

SOTECIN

FACTORY

D1.2 Data Management Plan V6.1

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D1.2 Data Management Plan

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GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description
DC	Data Controller
DM	Data Manager
DMP	Data Management Plan
DP	Data Processor
DPO	Data Protection Officer
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IH	Impact Hub
MV	Metabolic Ventures
PC	Project Coordinator
VPN	Virtual Private Network
WP	Work Package

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Objectives and Scope

Project SoTecln Factory will promote a collaborative approach to social innovation with highly scalable technologies, aiming to construct innovative solutions to transform value chains. The main goal of the project is to create the SoTecln Factory Community – a collaborative environment to improve resilience and sustainability of the European industry. SoTecln Factory will support a community of mission-oriented social innovators, connecting them to technology providers and industrial companies, towards turning ideas that aim to increase the circularity of key product value chains into pre-market demonstrations. The SoTecln Factory focuses on seven key product value chains, as defined by the EU Circular Economy Action Plan: (1) Electronics and ICT, (2) Batteries and vehicles, (3) Packaging, (4) Plastics, (5) Textiles, (6) Construction and buildings, (7) Food, water and nutrients. Through two open calls, SoTecln will present Value Chain Circular Challenges that will be solved by the solutions presented by social Innovators. Considering that this value chain transformation should be long-term and lasting, SoTecln Factory will embed the stewardship-council principles at both a mission and venture level of the social innovators, thus maximizing chances of long-term lasting systemic changes. Finally, SoTecln will provide financial and capacity-building assistance to social innovators, supporting mission-oriented pre-market demonstration projects.

The current version of the SoTecln Factory Data Management Plan presents basilar data management procedures to be adopted throughout the life-cycle of the project data. Among other aspects, it outlines a preliminary assessment of the data exchanged in SoTecln Factory, including scientific research, surveys with external stakeholders, open call applications, etc. It focuses particularly in the activities to disseminate FAIR data, such as the repository service available for the project, the metadata profile and data citation standard. Moreover, it establishes the foundations for data security.

The methodology adopted for developing this version of the DMP consisted in mapping good data management practices and aligning them with the structural components of the DMP, as recommended by the EC. The following versions of the DMP will build on the core practices described in this document, evolving into more specific ones as the project evolves.

The DMP is designed to be a living document that will be updated annually, with respect to the different phases of the SoTecln Factory methodology, depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Overall methodology of the SoTecln Factory

INESC TEC will assign a Data Manager (DM) with the overall responsibility of ensuring that the DMP is implemented and by carrying out its periodic reviews. The DMP will specify, among others, how the data will be safely stored, and how the data will be prepared for archiving, or sharing, after the end of the project. Given that SoTecln Factory will manage individual data related to the Open Calls (tech-savvy innovators) and to the implementation of demonstrators, the DM will also be responsible for ensuring that participants are provided with relevant information on the processing of their personal data as well as for ensuring the implementation in the project of defined guidelines and policies designed for the purpose of privacy and data protection compliance and the ethical use of data. Where applicable, metadata structure and formatting will follow standard practices to ensure replicability and anonymity, following Intellectual Property Rights and data protection concerns of involved stakeholders (e.g. data from individual participants of open calls and demonstrators, worker's data from demonstrators).

Collecting and processing data from the participants of the open calls and the networks of the SoTecln community is a crucial activity of the project and, as such, it requires an appropriate quality management of data collection and sharing within the consortium. For that reason, to complement INESC TEC's Data Management Activities, other partners of SoTecln Factory involved in the creation of the SoTecln Factory Community (Phase #1) – Impact Hub¹, F6S² and BWCON³ – also have an assigned data manager and their Data Policies publicly available, in compliance with the applicable laws and the agreements established at the consortium level. F6S will also use its platform to manage the application process of the techy-savvy innovators (Phase #3).

1.2. Structure of the DMP

The SoTecln Factory DMP is structured as follows:

- The Data Summary section outlines the data expected to be collected throughout the project.
- The FAIR data section provides a description of the data sharing principles of the project, that is, how the data generated by the project will be made available (repository services). It includes good data management practices to be adopted by the project, with respect to data licensing and identifiers. Finally, this section presents the data documentation strategy, with the different levels of data documentation, file name convention and metadata standards.
- The Data Organization and Security section aims to introduce high-level data storage, backup and access control planning.
- The Ethics and legal compliance section provide a description of procedures to manage sensitive and personal data. It mostly consists of the practices regarding the implementation of ethical and legal principles for dealing with data collected from human participants. Additional security measures may be included in this section, from time to time, following the DPO's recommendations, complementing the previous section in what regards the security standards to be applied to personal data processing in the project.

¹ <https://impacthub.net/websites-privacy-policy/>

² <https://www.f6s.com/privacy-policy>

³ <https://www.bwcon.de/datenschutz>

2. DATA SUMMARY

This section will provide information about the dataset that the project will create, gather or reuse. It will provide an incremental inventory of the data updated in each version of the DMP. The following data is expected to be collected in the course of the project.

- Data from the different stakeholders of the SoTecIn Factory Community;
- Data gathered in Surveys and Workshops;
- Data from Challenge Owners⁴;
- Data from individual/company participants of open calls and demonstrators;
- Open Call evaluation dataset, and data from external experts
- Technical data from the demonstrators⁵;
- Scientific Articles and respective supporting data.
- Event registration and participation data
- Consents to use image and audio in dissemination actions
- Webinars and Video recorded meetings data
- Website and social media data analytics
- Data from professional contacts of the potential interested entities related to the relevant open calls and events.

2.1. Data Inventory Register

In order to gather information about the data collected or produced by SoTecIn Factory, a Data Inventory Register (DIR) is available in the INESC TEC drive. The DIR can be defined as a comprehensive catalogue of metadata, wherein information about the datasets can be updated. The information provided must be as rich as possible, and metadata fields must be filled in where applicable. The following metadata elements, depicted in table 1, are included in the DIR, and some of the information collected can then be used when sharing the datasets.

The information collected in the DIR will also be used to update the Data Summary section of this DMP, as the DMP will be used to keep track of the project’s data.

Table 1 – Data Inventory Register metadata elements

Information	Content
Partner Name	Example_ INESC TEC
Task-Subtask	The identification of the task or subtask in which the data was produced

⁴ Industrial and/or technological companies with an identified critical sustainability problem in one of the seven Key Product Value Chains.

⁵ Pre-Market feasibility presentation of a technological solution which is small in scale and with a short life cycle so that planning, financing and implementation are easier and quicker, compared to complete projects.

Responsible Party	The person(s) responsible for the creation/maintenance of the dataset
Dataset Name	A descriptive and relative short name for the dataset
Data Type	Example: experimental, observational, simulational, among other types
Personal Data	If the dataset contains information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person
Sensitive Data	Any data that reveals a subject's information. Namely, racial or ethnic origin, political and religious beliefs, biometric data, sexual orientation and others. Yes or No
Data Created	Date of creation of the dataset. Example YYYY-MM-DD
Number of Data Files	The total number of files that make up the dataset
Source	Where the dataset originates. Is the data reuse? Recommended best practice is to identify the related resource
Format	The file format
Size	The total weight of the dataset (when applicable)
Data Collection Instrument	The instrument used to generate and process the data
Support Documentation	Whether documents have been created to provide context for the data. For examples, experimental protocols and <i>readme.files</i>
Update Frequency	The frequency with which the data will be updated
Storage Location	Place where the data is stored. For instance, institutional drive
Preservation	Backup periodicity and for how long the dataset needs to be preserved
Availability	Private, consortium or open
Rights and Restrictions	Data licence, CC BY-SA 4.0 is recommended for data sharing.

Table 2 – SoTecln Factory Data Inventory Register (ongoing update)

Dataset	Descriptive Information	
Challenges Owner Members	<p>Data Type: Contact lists</p> <p>Date created: 2023-08-10</p> <p>Number of data files: 1</p> <p>Format: .xlsx</p> <p>Size .12kb</p> <p>Mode of data collection: Data collected from the individual network of consortium partners</p> <p>Data collection instrument: Through an online form resulting from an Open Call for Challenges Owners</p>	<p>Personal data: yes</p> <p>Update frequency: Will be updated during the second Open Call for Challenges Owners</p> <p>Storage location: INESC TEC Drive. Data is located outside the project shared folder, only accessible by the Project Coordinator, the data manager, the DMP manager and the responsible party.</p> <p>Backup: A regular backup is made according to INESC TEC’s policies applied to the online drive</p> <p>Availability: Private</p> <p>Rights and Restrictions; This dataset has restricted access to SoTecln Factory PM, DM and to the Dataset Owner</p>
Mission Council Members	<p>Data Type: Contact lists</p> <p>Date created: 2023-07-13</p> <p>Number of data files: 2</p> <p>Format: .xlsx</p> <p>Size .252kb</p> <p>Mode of data collection: Data collected from the individual network of consortium partners</p> <p>Data collection instrument: By e-mail</p>	<p>Personal data: yes</p> <p>Update frequency: Will not be updated</p> <p>Storage location: INESC TEC Drive. Data is located outside the project shared folder, only accessible by the Project Coordinator, the data manager, the DMP manager and the responsible party.</p> <p>Backup: A regular backup is made according to INESC TEC’s policies applied to the online drive.</p> <p>Availability; Private</p> <p>Rights and Restrictions; This dataset has restricted access to SoTecln Factory PM, DM and to the Dataset Owner</p>
SoTecln Factory Community	<p>Data Type: Contact lists</p> <p>Date created: 2023-08-10</p> <p>Number of data files: 9</p>	<p>Personal data: yes</p> <p>Update frequency: Will be updated every month</p> <p>Storage location: INESC TEC Drive. Data is located outside the project</p>

	<p>Format: .xlsx and pdf</p> <p>Size .334kb</p> <p>Mode of data collection: Data collected from the individual network of consortium partners</p> <p>Data collection instrument: By e-mail</p>	<p>shared folder, only accessible by the Project Coordinator, the data manager, the DMP manager and the responsible party.</p> <p>Backup: A regular backup is made according to INESC TEC’s policies applied to the online drive</p> <p>Availability: Private</p> <p>Rights and Restrictions; This dataset has restricted access to SoTecln Factory PM, DM and to the Dataset Owner</p>
<p>Tech-Savvy Innovators</p>	<p>Data Type: Contact lists</p> <p>Date created: 2023-10-06</p> <p>Number of data files: 1</p> <p>Format: .xlsx</p> <p>Size .301kb</p> <p>Mode of data collection: Data collected from the individual network of consortium partners</p> <p>Data collection instrument: Through online form resulting from the Open Calls for Social Innovators</p>	<p>Personal data: yes</p> <p>Update frequency: Will be updated during the second Open Call of SoTecln Factory</p> <p>Storage location: INESC TEC Drive. Data is located outside the project shared folder, only accessible by the Project Coordinator, the data manager, the DMP manager and the responsible party.</p> <p>Backup: A regular backup is made according to INESC TEC’s policies applied to the online drive</p> <p>Availability: Private</p> <p>Rights and Restrictions; This dataset has restricted access to SoTecln Factory PM, DM and to the Dataset Owner</p>

3. FAIR DATA

In this section, the guiding principles for promoting the FAIRness of SoTecln Factory data are outlined. It describes high-level practices on how the project intends to make the data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. It focuses, particularly, on the approach to adopt for project data that can be openly shared without restrictions, although the solutions described enable data protection measures.

3.1. SoTecIn Factory data sharing principles

SoTecIn Factory is committed to the following underlying principles to facilitate the dissemination and reusability of the project data:

- The data collected in the course of the project, except sensitive and personal data, will be made openly available, with respect to possible embargo periods, through data repository.
- Persistent identifiers are assigned to the shared data and included in its metadata.
- Metadata should be accessible even when the data may not be publicly available due to data protection issues.
- Metadata is based on standard vocabulary(ies), whenever possible.

3.2. Data availability

As a rule of thumb, the data generated by the project, provided it does not contain sensitive information, will be deposited, and preserved, in the data repository provided by INESC TEC (rdm.inesctec.pt), for at least 5 years after the end of the project.

The INESC TEC institutional data repository, based on the CKAN open source data management system, can be accessed by any user at any time and from any location. This repository will be used to deposit data related to the SoTecIn Factory Community and to the projects developed during the open calls. At INESC TEC the data backups are performed daily, while tape backup is performed weekly.

Not all data needs to be deposited for sharing and preservation purposes. For this reason, it is necessary to evaluate which data, and at what point in its life-cycle, should be deposited. Datasets can be deposited with private visibility, in order to respect eventual embargo periods and other access restrictions.

If necessary, the deposit of data in disciplinary data repositories is also open to accommodate possible data policy requirements while publishing project results. In this case, the project partners can deposit the data in the repositories recommended by the publishers, if they recommend any, or the selection of a disciplinary repository can be made via the data repositories directory [re3data.org](https://www.re3data.org/) (<https://www.re3data.org/>).

3.3. Scientific Publication Data

A balanced approach between the adoption of Open Science practices and the assurance of the Intellectual Property Rights of all stakeholders and the participants' privacy rights will be adopted in the SoTecIn Factory project, aligned with the EU data sharing policy on the principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary". Open access implies unrestricted online access to research outputs such as journal articles, without access fees. The goal is to foster access to and re-use of data generated by EU funded projects, in order to improve and maximize public financial European resources and avoid duplication of efforts.

With respect to SoTeIn Factory publications, they can be published in open access journals best suited to the publication at hand. This option is encouraged to all project partners. This means the journal should grant open access by definition. These are normally:

- Conference proceedings;
- Open access journals with no Article Processing Charges (APC);
- Open access journals with "low cost" APCs.

Peer reviewed scientific publications will be provided with the highest standard (gold) when possible, that means a higher fee is paid and the publication is granted open access immediately. Publications can also be published in green open access mode, that means the publication can be made available after an embargo period, which is set up by the publisher.

The partners understand intellectual property as a crucial aspect when it comes to foster knowledge co-creation and are fully committed to ensure its accomplishment. Open science will be implemented as an integral part of the project by means of three main practices that help to improve the transparency and accessibility of the scientific research and, as consequence, increase both its validity and recognition within the academic community and its social contribution:

1. Preregistration – where possible, the hypotheses and objectives that arise from the research in the context of the project will be developed and published before their test as a way to assure the transparency of the process. Similarly, all the methodological procedures, including the data analysis plan, will be publicly registered prior to conducting the study. These practices help to ensure that the objectives and methods are not changed along the research. An online platform will be used to preregister the research intentions (e.g. <https://aspredicted.org/>).
2. Open data – open data will be considered an alternative during the project when applicable, assuring the Intellectual Property Rights of all stakeholders and considering data ownership issues.
3. Open access – preference will be given to publish the results of research in the context of the project with open access. Pre-prints will also be considered as an option to publish results.

3.4. Zenodo Community

Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>), the catch-all repository for EC funded research, will be considered as the service to support the dissemination of project achievements. These outputs can take the form of processed data, research protocols, reports, the different version of the DMP itself, among other artefacts.

A SoTeIn Factory was created for the exclusive use of sharing research outputs related to the project. The publication of content submitted by project partners requires the approval of the community curator, and DMP manager, João Aguiar Castro. The links to the SoTeIn Community within Zenodo are as follows:

- Community collection: <https://zenodo.org/communities/stif>
- Upload URL: <https://zenodo.org/uploads/new?community=stif>

Each partner is required to create an account in order to upload respective Open Access publications, Open Access datasets or a validated public deliverable. SoTecln Factory is a “community” within Zenodo where all scientific publications will be uploaded.

By using the Upload URL for the community, project partners will directly deposit their outputs in the SoTecln Factory community. In each deposit it has to be guaranteed that:

- The DOI is reserved;
- The SoTecln Factory grant number is included, since Zenodo integrates this information into reporting lines for research funded by the EU, as depicted in Figure 2;
- Use of ORCID information.

Figure 2 - Adding Funding Identifier in Zenodo upload

Publications and data uploaded on Zenodo are indexed automatically in the OpenAire aggregator and will be automatically synchronized with the European Commission participant portal, hence there is no need to update information on scientific publications for reporting purposes.

In addition to Zenodo, project partners might want to use other platforms to upload data or publications. Further repositories for data are available within the “re3data” registry (www.re3data.org) and OpenAire (www.openaire.eu). Project partners are encouraged to disseminate outputs also in web-based scientific social networks such as www.academia.org or www.researchgate.net

In the case of data, publishing the same dataset at both INESC TEC and Zenodo introduces redundancy of preservation and greater scope for data dissemination.

Table 3 will update the project outputs available in Zenodo.

Table 3 – SoTecln Factory outputs in Zenodo

Outputs	Responsible
Presentation	
The role of R-strategies for circular supply chains – a systematic review	Ana Inês
Pitch Presentation – SoTecln Factory project	Milana Sekulic
Project Deliverables	

D2.3. Report with new business models	Melisa Oezkan
D2.2. Final Guidelines "Principles for mission-oriented social innovation through stewardship model"	Ana Raguž

3.5. Identifier

The DOIs for the data that will be deposited in the INESC TEC data repository will be registered and managed via DataCite Fabrica (<https://doi.datacite.org/>), a service provided by the leading provider of research data DOIs. By the time a dataset reaches the publication stage, the DM will trigger the process of minting a DOI, by filling out a set of metadata associated with the dataset, which must include the minimal citation elements.

Complementarily, outputs directly deposited in Zenodo will be granted a DOI generated by the service.

3.6. Citation

The following minimal data citation elements are recommended, according to the DataCite (APA reference style).

- Creator (PublicationYear): Title, Publisher. DOI

The SoTecln Factory dataset titles must indicate the subject matter, the geography and the time period covered by the data, when applicable. Additional properties may also be added, such as Version and Resource Type.

3.7. Data documentation

Data sharing within and outside of the project must include metadata, along with the needed documentation for others to understand and reuse the data. SoTecln Factory data has to be documented at various levels and a *readme.txt* file, in the absence of other type of file, should be a common practice to accompany the datasets, being included in a common folder, at the time of sharing and/or publishing the datasets.

Some information may already be integrated in the software or platforms where the data will be made available, namely in the metadata provided by the INESC TEC data repository (see Table 1). **Erro! A origem da referência não foi encontrada.**

Data documentation should consider the following information:

- **At task level**
 - A technical report for the user to understand how the data were collected and processed.

- Citation information to indicate how secondary users will have to cite the data.
- Study design, methodologies, instruments and measures used.
- **File or database level**
 - Information on how the files that make up the dataset (or tables in a database) relate to each other.
 - The format of the files.
- **Variable or item level**
 - Information on how the object of analysis was produced.
 - Full label explaining the meaning of variables.

3.8. Metadata standards

Both the INESC TEC data repository and Zenodo already follow appropriate metadata standards, specifically Dublin Core, a highly adopted, domain-agnostic metadata standard, published as ISO Standard 15836 :2017 (<https://www.iso.org/standard/71339.html>). Metadata records based on the Dublin Core standard ensure that project data is more easily findable and also interoperable.

Metadata standards for describing specific project data should be evaluated on a case-by-case basis and reflected in upcoming versions of the DMP. The Metadata Standards Directory can be consulted to assess suitable domain-specific standards to promote data reuse. Additional custom metadata fields can be added in the INESC TEC data repository, to address specific metadata requirements.

For the deposit of a dataset in the INESC TEC data repository a metadata template will be made available, by the DM. This template is to be filled by the data responsible before the deposit. Table 2 details the core metadata elements in the INESC TEC data repository. The DM will maintain an inventory of all the data deposited, and essential metadata, in the SoTecln Factory drive.

Table 4 - Metadata elements in the INESC TEC data repository template

Metadata Element	Content
Visibility	Public or Private
Title	The title of the dataset
Tags – Subject	Topics related to the dataset
License	Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike as default
Version	The version of the dataset
Author	The person(s) responsible for creating the dataset
Author Email	The contact of the responsible for creating the dataset
Maintainer	The person responsible of the management of the dataset
Contributor	An entity responsible for making contributions to the dataset

Spatial Coverage	Spatial characteristics of the dataset
Temporal Coverage	Temporal characteristics of the dataset
Type of Instrument	Type of instrument used for data collection or capture
Creation Date	Date of creation of the resource. YYYY-MM-DD
Format	The file format, physical medium, or dimensions of the resource
Publisher	An entity responsible for making the resource available
Relation	A related resource. Recommended practice is to identify the related resource by means of a URI. A string may be used conforming to a formal identification system.
Type	Dataset as default
Source	The source from which the described dataset is derived
File Size	The total volume of the dataset (how much storage it consumes). It can also provide information regarding the duration of the dataset
Software	Computer program used to generate and run the resource

4. DATA ORGANIZATION AND SECURITY

This section provides an overview of data security measures to be adopted in SoTecIn Factory regarding data organization, storage and backup, as well as access controls.

4.1. File Naming

In order to understand what a data file is and its content, file names have to remain meaningful and useful beyond their original creation and storage – in other words SoTecIn Factory data has to outlast the person who created the file. When adopting file name conventions and standards, project partners must create a simple quick access guide to be displayed in the SoTecIn Factory drive, to ensure that others can easily access and understand the data, and to protect against data loss.

There are several elements that must be consider in the implementation of the file name strategy. On its own, the filename should convey metadata about the data file.

- Description of the content
- Name of creator (initials)
- Name of research team associated with the data
- Date of creation; Publication data
- Version number

However, some conditions must be guaranteed.

- Context information. Data file names have to include specific or descriptive information. For instance, using (I03), where (I) refers to the interview (data type) and 03 refers to participants or interviews order.
- Consistency. The adopted convention has to be followed systematically.
- Short and relevant names. By norm, 25 characters is enough to convey descriptive information.
- The use of special characters is to avoid. These are often for other specific tasks in different operating systems.
- The use of underscore or hyphen are recommended over full-stops or spaces. The latter are parsed differently on different systems.

Regarding the SoTecIn Factory deliverable, the naming standard will be:

- DX.X_SOTECIN_NameOfDocument_Partner_VX
 - ex: D1.2_SOTECIN_DataManagementPlan_INESCTEC_V1

4.2. File date formatting

If necessary, dates included in the file name have to follow the format Year-Month-Day, to maintain the chronological order and simplify the process of sorting and browsing data files.

By adopting this convention SoTeIn Factory ensures compliance with the international standard for the representation of date and time, ISO 8601 (<https://www.iso.org/iso-8601-date-and-time-format.html>).

- YYYY-MM-DD
- YYYY-MM
- YYYY-YYYY
- YYYY-MM-DD-DAY-HOUR

4.3. Versioning

The versioning of the documents should follow the rules below:

- First version of the document should use V1
 - Ex.: D1.1_SOTECIN_DataManagementPlan_INESC TEC_V1
- Minor modifications should be assigned in decimals
 - Ex.: D1.1_SOTECIN_DataManagementPlan_INESC TEC_V1.1
- When the document is fully reviewed / edited by a different author it should then be assigned as a new version
 - Ex.: D1.1_SOTECIN_DataManagementPlan_INESC TEC_V2
- When closing the document for submission, use VF

ex: D1.2_SOTECIN_DataManagementPlan_INESC TEC_VF

4.4. Storage and backup

To prevent against the risk of data loss, SoTeIn Factory data will be stored in institutional network drives (INESC TEC drive), that must be routinely backed up and provide account authentication systems to prevent unauthorised access, preferably by resorting to strong passwords. It is highly recommended to store data in centrally-managed network drives, thus ensuring the storage of data in a single place. Moreover, when researchers are working off-site, data must be available via VPN.

To manage and share data securely, certain data storage platforms are not recommended for long-term storage of SoTeIn Factory data, such as:

- External portable storage devices, such as external hard drives and USB drives, given their longevity uncertainty and how easily these can be damaged or lost;
- Popular cloud storage platforms, aimed for the general public.

Personal storage devices, such as PCs and Laptops, are convenient for short-term storage and data processing yet, these fall outside the scope of the DMP. However, project partners must ensure that the backup of data is regularly made through suitable networked drives. Data backups should be made regularly and data must be stored at least in two different media one off-site. During the execution of SoTeIn Factory, the backup of data stored at the INESC TEC drive will be conducted as following:

- Daily backup of network drives, as primary data storage device.

- Weekly backup to tape cartridge, for long-term off-site data preservation

The INESC TEC data repository and Zenodo are complementary services for preservation and sharing purposes of selected data at a later stage of their life-cycle.

4.5. Access controls

Access controls require some form of authentication. For greater security, an (external) user account has to be created for individuals who require access to data. Additionally, the activities associated with specific accounts must be logged for accountability purposes.

Managing permissions to specific files will also have to be considered, for a more granular control of who is able to handle specific datasets. When working collaboratively, it is recommended that file access protocols specify that only one user can have access to data at a time. Further details regarding access controls should be developed in upcoming versions of the DMP.

Suitable strong passwords are a very important aspect of data security. When specifying passwords SoTecln Factory partners must consider the following:

- Use of a mix of upper-and-lower-case letters, numbers and punctuation marks;
- Use of some non-alphabetic characters, e.g. @\$%+/- (minimum of 20);
- Use of non-dictionary words.

Passwords managers are suitable tools to support the handling of strong passwords.

5. ETHICS AND LEGAL COMPLIANCE

In SoTeIn Factory, human participants will be involved by means of interviews and workshops. Hence, SoTeIn Factory entails a series of ethical and legal principles and regulations that govern the overall implementation of the project activities. In addition to the measures mentioned in the previous section (Data Organization and Security), this section outlines key aspects to guide the processing of personal data, always with respect to the applicable legal framework, in particular the GDPR and the Partners national legislation.

Accordingly, the partners will ensure that:

- All personal data processing must comply with the GDPR principles. These include fairness, lawfulness and transparency; purpose limitation; data minimisation; data quality; security, integrity and confidentiality.
- The basis for processing personal data within the project is the informed consent (express, specific) of data subjects, as established by the GDPR.
- For each activity that involves data collection, the Data Controllers and Data Processors are clearly defined
- For the release of any data that includes personal data, not only must the released data be anonymised, but also such opening of the data and subsequent processing must fall within the limits permitted by the GDPR (consent for anonymisation or permitted “further processing”).
- No personal sensitive data (defined by Article 9 of the GDPR as “data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, (...) genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person’s sex life or sexual orientation”) will be collected by the SoTeIn Factory project.
- Each partner will notify to the DM and the Data Protection Officer (DPO) in its organisation.
- Record keeping of all personal data processing activities in compliance with GDPR.

5.1. Roles and Responsibilities in the management of personal data

The GDPR defines certain roles in relation to the processing of personal data, to whom a number of specific legal obligations are attached to.

A Data Controller (DC) is an institution or body that determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data. In particular, the controller has to implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure and to be able to demonstrate that processing is performed in compliance with the applicable law, namely, considering the nature, scope, context and purposes of the processing as well as the risks involved for data subjects.

A Data Processor (DP) is a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or any other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller; the data processor must follow the licit instructions given by the data controller. A processor shall not engage another processor without prior authorisation from the controller.

Project partners as data controllers (either separate or joint controllers) will be responsible for ensuring the lawful processing of the respective datasets as well as for the implementation of security, technical and organizational measures to ensure the security of project data and avoid its alteration, loss, and / or unauthorized access, given the state of technology, the nature of the data stored and the risks they are exposed to, whether from human action or the physical or natural. Moreover, the need for conducting data protection impact assessments will be assessed by each of the project partners as data controllers

Following the provisions already defined in the Consortium Agreement, through the establishment of specific data sharing agreements (including joint controller or data processing agreements when required), the project partners will be able to further specify rules and procedures regarding data processing activities in the project, in order to ensure compliance with data protection principles and legal framework.

Nonetheless, among the best practices implemented in the consortium, all data exchanged between the participants and the partners shall be duly protected by the use of certifiable, anonymized, encoded or encrypted data exchange mechanisms. Whenever anonymization is not possible, pseudonymisation will be used to prevent the direct association between the pilot participants and the collected or exchanged information. Authentication and security certificates will be used to guarantee high levels of data protection methods.

Institutions collecting personal data are required to have a person responsible to monitor GDPR compliance, the above-mentioned DM, who will, when necessary, consult with the DPO of the institution when applicable. The DM will ensure that the project personal data policies are implemented, in order to keep data accurate and up to date as well as to ensure the integrity and confidentiality of the data.

Collected data will be encrypted to ensure that it cannot be accessed by non-authorized people. It is recommended the **creation of encrypted data containers and securely store sensitive data files** inside them (encrypting single files is not recommended).

Personal data will be stored in specific folders inside the INESC TEC's shared drive, but with access limited to the PC and the DM.

5.2. Data Minimization

Following a key principle in data protection law, SoTeIn Factory will only collect essential personal information data, and this data shall be retained no longer than necessary. This means that personal data should only be kept for the time necessary to carry out the purposes for which it was collected, or the time required to comply with applicable law.

Personal data must be reviewed periodically to decide whether unnecessary identifying information is retained. Data retention limits are set until the end of the period needed to conduct the research. When identifying information is no longer needed, data shall be anonymised or be safely deleted or destroyed.

When applicable, and with the consent of the participants, audio recordings of interviews will be transcribed and coded, as soon as possible, and then deleted by the end of the project.

Conventional file deletion is not enough to ensure that the data cannot be recovered. To securely destroy the data, additional steps will be adopted, namely:

- The use of appropriate software;
- Encryption key deletion, to prevent the recovery of data stored in an encrypted container or disk.

Specific data protection procedures for the destruction of data has to be defined in compliance with GDPR and the applicable legal framework. Proof of data destruction shall be provided by the partner involved in the process. A **Certificate of Data Destruction** template will be prepared for the use by the partners within the project.

5.3. Anonymisation

For sharing or publishing SoTecln Factory sensitive data, without revealing the confidential information it contains, data anonymisation procedures must be carried out by project partners.

As soon as the identifying information is no longer needed, direct identifiers should be removed, where possible, by deleting them or replacing them with pseudonyms. Direct identifiers expected to be generated by SoTecln Factory personal data, include:

- First name
- Last name
- ID
- Email address
- Phone number
- Physical features, voice, photos or other images.

5.4. Privacy by Design and by default

In the case of qualitative data, identifying characteristics must be replaced or generalised. To do a pseudo-anonymization of the personal, and sensitive data, collected data will be treated with a code. Thus, linkage files, containing information to link data subjects to identifiable individuals, must be encrypted and stored securely and separately from the de-identified data.

Particularly attention should be paid to indirect identifiers, such as *age*, *education* and *employment* information, that, if drawn from small populations, extreme values or rare characteristics can still made it possible to identify subjects. In this case, advanced anonymization techniques may be considered.

For datasets reaching the publication stage, **only aggregated (anonymised) data and non-identifiable datasets' metadata could be made available.**

5.5. Informed Consent for participation and the processing of personal data

Given that SoTecIn Factory will conduct in depth interviews and surveys with external stakeholders, an Informed Consent form will be sent to all participants prior to their access to the survey or the interviews. The informed consent process makes sure that the external participants to the research conducted by SoTecIn Factory had access to all the necessary information about the project and the data processing before they decide to participate and give their consent to the processing of personal data. The template which will be used as an informed Consent is available in Annex I.

5.6. International transfers of data

No international data transfers are envisaged in the project.

5.7. Data subjects' rights

Each project partner acting as a data controller must put in place adequate procedures to ensure respect for data subjects rights enshrined in the GDPR. When in a context of joint controllership, joint controllers will define a common point of contact for data subjects, in order to ease the exercise of data subjects' rights.

ANNEXES

ANNEX I – Consent Form

INFORMED CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE IN A RESEARCH PROJECT
<p>Please read the following information. If you think something is incorrect or unclear, don't hesitate to ask for more information through the email: gustavo.dalmarco@inesctec.pt</p> <p>If you wish to participate in the study we request your consent, which you can give by signing the document.</p> <p>Participation in the study is voluntary. You can quit it at any time without any consequence, needing only to contact the person responsible through the email specified above.</p>
<p>1.PROJECT DESCRIPTION</p>
<p>Title: SoTecln Factory - Social and Technological Innovation Factory for Low-Carbon and Circular Industrial Value Chains</p> <p>Responsible Entity: INESC TEC, CNR</p> <p>Principal Investigator: <i>Gustavo Dalmarco</i> - gustavo.dalmarco@inesctec.pt</p> <p>General Description: <i>This study focuses the analysis and characterization of the main strategies for the creation or transformation of Circular Value Chains, identifying its barriers and Challenges. This is a Horizon Europe Funded project, with 36 months of duration, coordinated by INESC TEC. The other members of the consortium are CNR, F6S, Metabolic, Impact Hub and BWCON.</i></p>
<p>2.PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA</p>
<p>Project Objectives:</p> <p><i>The main objective of the data collection is to understand the characteristics of circular value chains, and the main challenges and barriers to a circular transformation. In that sense the data collected is mainly related to the knowledge and experience of the interviewee about value chains and circular transformation.</i></p> <p>Personal Data:</p> <p><i>Personal information such as name, address, contact information and other direct personal identifiers will be collected to qualify the relevance of the interviewees, but it will not be mentioned in any publication or dissemination of the research data and/or results by INESC TEC. We will interview representatives of relevant Value Chains, discussing the main circular objectives of 7 key product value chains, as defined by the EU Circular Economy Action Plan: (1) Electronics and ICT, (2) Batteries and vehicles, (3) Packaging, (4) Plastics, (5) Textiles, (6) Construction and buildings, (7) Food, water and nutrients.</i></p> <p><i>Interviews will have duration of 60 minutes, and they will be carried out via a video conferencing software. In the beginning of the interview, we will ask participants (1) to assure they are aware</i></p>

about the consent document, demonstrating their knowledge of the purpose of the study, and (2) to confirm whether they permit us to record the interview for accuracy. Interviewees will be reminded that they have the right to request the recording of the interview, or to stop the recording at any time to make a statement off the record. The interviews will be transcribed and coded in order to extract relevant insights for the research.

Purposes of Personal Data Processing:

The data collected will be processed according to the applicable national and EU legislation and will only be used by the investigators for the purpose of scientific research within the domain of circular value chains and social innovation.

Responsible for the Processing:

INESC TEC - Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores, Tecnologia e Ciência, Campus da FEUP, Rua Dr. Roberto Frias, 4200 - 465 Porto.

Personal Data Retention Period:

Personal data will be stored in the virtual drive of INESC TEC property, with limited access to those directly involved in the data collection process, and will not be disclosed to third parties. After the analysis of the interviews the recordings will be permanently deleted.

Security Measures:

The researchers will take the following steps to protect participants' identities during this study: (1) Each participant will be assigned a number and the researchers will record any data collected during the study that number, not by name (pseudonymisation); (2) all and any original recordings or data files will be stored in a secured virtual drive located in INESC TEC' servers; (3) only authorized researchers will have access to those files or any other data processed.

Personal Data Sharing:

The content of the interviews will only be handled by those directly involved in the data collection and analysis. No personal data will be shared with other entities that establish research partnerships with INESC TEC, nor transferred to entities established in countries outside the European Union. Only the consolidated results of all interviews will be shared in the context of meetings, or dissemination of results in scientific journals or academic publications.

Data Protection Officer:

For any questions regarding the processing of your personal data, please contact our Data Protection Officer at: dpo@inesctec.pt

Rights of the Data Subject:

As the subject of the data, the law grants you the following rights: Information, Access, Rectification, Portability, Erasure, and Restriction of processing. To exercise any of your rights please use the following email address: dpo@inesctec.pt.

Under the terms of the Article 77 of the GDPR, the data subject has the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority in the European Union. In Portugal, the supervisory authority is the CNPD (www.cnpd.pt).

3. INFORMED CONSENT FORM

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I read and understand the information about the project, including the identity of the controller, the type of data collected, the purpose of the collection and the respective processing. 2. I read and understand the information about how the data is stored and for how long, including what will happen to my data in the case of ceasing my participation in the project. 3. I have been given the opportunity to ask questions and to clarify any doubts about the project. 4. I understand I can quit participating in the project at any point, without needing to provide any justification and without suffering any penalty or having my motives questioned. 5. I understand how to communicate my decision to quit, as well as how to exercise my rights as the data subject. 	<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
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The Participant:

I declare I have read and understood this document, as well as the verbal information that have been given to me previously. As such, I accept to participate in this study and allow the use of the data I offer voluntarily.

Name:

Signature: Date: / /